

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MUSAU****FIRST NAME: SARAH****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER:1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Word 365

HONING YOUR ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS

1) INTRODUCTION

Instructed by Dr Kabiru Gulma, ACA-401D period one intended for students to master effective academic and professional writing in an international context. It majorly focused on familiarity and readings of EUCLID's coursepack (2019), Zotero training video, and the Turabian's Manual for Writers of Research papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers (2013) which I notably focused on in this response paper.

The manual offered extensive practical guidelines and solutions for student writers, detailing the recommended conventions of writing from research planning to source citations to styles of writing (Turabian 2013, 24). Part one of the manual extensively covered guidelines in their simplest version for student writers, providing a road map to the process of research, development of arguments, and formulation of questions. For those who may have taken a break from academic writing or research in general, this section is quite helpful. I particularly found it greatly beneficial and a good start to all my academic and research-related needs. Part two of the manual covered source citations, clearly detailing the differences between notes-bibliography style and parenthetical citations-reference list style as well as utilization of digital sources, previously not covered in the earlier editions. Part three refreshingly covered styles of writing from punctuation to spelling to abbreviations (Ibid.).

2) **ACADEMIC WRITING PREPARATION**

Academic writing may prove difficult especially if you come from a background that did not call for research, or if you had taken a break from academia. Part one of the Turabian's manual highlights critical points on how to prepare for research despite your background. It specifically calls for planning, broken down into specific steps. "You cannot plunge into a project blindly; you must plan it, then keep the whole process in mind as you take each step. So, think big, but break the process down into small goals that you can meet one at a time" (Turabian 2013, 30). Similarly, EUCLID points out that, a well written academic paper involves proper planning. "An essay plan can help you work out how you will answer the question and which information you will use. Essay plans also help with structuring an essay" (EUCLID 2019, 6). The fact that I am in the early months of my doctoral journey, this section has helped me embrace the habit of breaking down tasks for all my academic papers as well as my professional tasks especially funding proposals. This knowledge inspired me to download various apps such as the smartsheet, notepad, and sticky notes which as much as I knew about them, I did not extensively use them. For this assignment, I used sticky notes to organize my work. I began by working on the body, the conclusion, and then the summary, clearly noting down all the references. What particularly marvelled me was the degree of concentration when you work on a step by step approach. "You can handle any project if you break it into its parts, then work on them one step at a time" (Turabian 2013, 30).

Before joining EUCLID, I had developed a research plan for my dissertation. However, I had not considered that I needed to do the same for other academic papers such as a response paper. I thought I could just go through the given reading materials, summarize then submit. No, I was wrong. I tried to do that, and it turned out disastrous. It was not until I decided to completely and keenly read the Turabian manual that I woke up to reality of academic papers. I found myself reading external materials from other sources to get in-depth understanding of response papers, as well as planning process in all the work (Turabian 2013, 34).

To be able to break down the paper into various steps, you need to feel in control of your writing, of your project. This is not necessarily easy, however, writing a response paper may make one to. As highlighted, "writing a response paper requires a description of your experiences, ideas, feelings, and life" ((EUCLID 2020, 3). "With ...(that) you will come to feel in control of your projects and not intimidated by them" (Turabian 2013, 31). Initially I doubted whether I could develop a response paper and realistically feel in control of it. Astoundingly, as I kept working on it, I found myself describing myself, my experiences, my fears, and my hopes. It gave me the overall feeling of the Ph.D. program. I have found myself practice writing daily. Excellence in academic writing necessitates a daily practice (Ibid.).

3) ACADEMIC WRITING SPECIFICITY

To develop a solid research project, collection of data is not necessarily the only important component. It goes beyond source citations (Turabian 2013, 41). In the Turabian manual, various approaches were discussed on how to prepare for a project. Of the most importance is the development of specific goals for your research (Turabian 2013, 42). Most of my previous work experience entailed fundraising and resource mobilization with a specific focus on development of competitive funding proposals and concept notes. Before drafting, I would write down specific goals for the proposal and the organization. I would then share the call for proposal with the staff to brainstorm after which I would visit the donor's website and afterward review the organization's previous reports and proposals. Depending on the donor, a funding proposal requires an appealing title, a problem statement, objectives, a logical framework, and a detailed budget. After going through the manual, I realized the specific goals outlined were what I had all along been applying in my work, and which made a solid proposal (Ibid.). I particularly found EUCLID's checklist quite beneficial in development of solid academic papers (EUCLID 2020, 4). It provided a clear perspective which made me rethink about academic writing. The fact that I have learned this in the early months of my doctoral program, I am elated to put them in practice early enough not just for a concrete dissertation but also for other academic papers.

However, there is no one size fits all in research. "No book can prepare you for every aspect of every research project. Research and reporting are never straightforward. You may need to read and re-read, change topics, and sometimes even change the whole research concept. Research is looping, messy, and unpredictable" (Turabian 2013, 31, 42). While developing this paper, I found myself learning and unlearning, changing sentences, and even at some point, redoing the paragraphs. This experience taught me the need to remain flexible whenever approaching any academic writing. "Work from a plan, but be ready to depart from it, even to discard it for a new one" (Ibid.). Similarly, EUCLID points out that, "as you begin to write and research your plan will probably change" (2019, 6).

4) ACADEMIC WRITING AUTHENTICITY

At the United States International University, we were exposed to only the American Psychological Association (APA) and the Modern Language Association (MLA) rules of citations, styles I have since used for all my papers. Part two of the Turabian's manual assiduously explained the difference between the two Turabian styles of citations, that is, parenthetical citations-reference list style and notes-bibliography style. Though at my previous universities I did hear of Chicago rule of style, Turabian which is EUCLID's recommended rule of style is a new word to me, and which to my amazement is the same as the Chicago style (EUCLID 2019, 29). "While sometimes reference is made to a "Turabian style," this is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers" (EUCLID 2013, 49). Notably, the notes-bibliography style

recommended for all EUCLID's major papers and the dissertation is a style I had not considerably utilized before and one that I intend to continue learning about (2019, 6).

Regardless of what kind of academic paper you are writing, acknowledging the source of your citation is irrefutably necessary. It is deemed ethical and the recognized standard for quality academic papers (Turabian 2013, 193). According to EUCLID, "all academic essays MUST contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offense" (2019, 9). Citations may take the form of a quote, paraphrase, or summary (Turabian 2013, 129). A recommended approach to including all cited sources is through noting down or use of management software (Turabian 2013, 70). The manual recommends programs such as EndNote, RefWorks, and Zotero for collection of data and citing (Turabian 2013, 201). EUCLID recommends the use of Zotero. Although I have not interacted with any of these before, I am open to learning and utilizing all of them in my doctoral journey. The provided EUCLID Zotero training video presented great insights on how to go about documenting and citing my sources, which I strove to use in this assignment. Although I encountered some challenges while using it, I feel it is a convenient program for anyone venturing into research.

EUCLID envisages for its students to observe rules of citations. The first day I received and skimmed through the student orientation guideline, I noticed EUCLID's expectation of high calibre graduates. This is reflected from their provision of Zotero and Grammarly tools, the recommendation of JSTOR and Questia, and customized templates. The student's orientation guideline categorically states that "EUCLID expects absolute compliance of the strict copyright regulations including acceptable international fair use guidelines, just as it expects full compliance with strict plagiarism and academic integrity guidelines" (2019, 2). Through its coursepack, EUCLID emphasizes that, "plagiarism is wrong and unethical, a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences, it is not fair to take someone's work and not give them credit" (2019, 10). I believe with continued practice; I will master the provided guidelines and tools within the shortest time possible to ease in writing effective academic papers as well as in developing my dissertation paper.

5) ACADEMIC WRITING EXQUISTINESS

Part three of the Turabian's manual extensively discussed on styles of writing, providing references in which a writer may consult on spelling-Webster's Third New International Dictionary or its abridgment, the eleventh edition of Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionary. "When in doubt, consult a dictionary" (Turabian 2013, 375). Although I had not bought or downloaded the above-recommended dictionaries, EUCLID's expectation of quality academic work made me plan on acquiring one. One of the expected outcomes of the ACA-401D course is that students should be able to differentiate and use either the US or the UK conventions of grammar and mechanics (EUCLID 2019, 32).

This is my area of concern and one I hope it will not negatively impact my doctoral journey. I was born in Kenya where I grew up speaking, writing, and learning

the UK's conventions of grammar at both elementary and secondary schools. I then joined United States International University an American institution that required usage of US conventions of grammar. At some point, I worked for the British High Commission where I was supposed to use UK's English. From the commission, I joined the UN in New York where I went back to US English. Most times I have mixed these conventions unintentionally. I feel this is the area that I need to dedicate time during these first few months of my doctoral journey. I am glad that it is taught in this first course and hope to master both. Also, the provision of EUCLID's Grammarly, customized templates, and recommendation of Write Source 2000 comes in handy as I kick off my doctoral journey.

6) CONCLUSION

Both the Turabian manual and ACA-401D coursepack provides simple guidelines on research, theses, and dissertations that are easy for students at any level of their research. However, the manual does acknowledge that the guidelines are not a one size fits all, and university's and instructor's guidelines precede theirs. "The guidelines may be supplemented or overruled by the conventions of specific disciplines or the preferences of particular institutions or departments" (Turabian 2013, 26). According to EUCLID, "the lack of a single authoritative source on style for written English means that there is, and will always be, a certain amount of debate on elements of style" (EUCLID 2019, 29).

I have found the manual to be simple to understand and one that I would repeatedly refer to master on excellent academic writing. Considering that I had taken a break from academic writing, these guidelines remind me of the journey ahead and expectation of producing quality doctoral work. The fact that I was accustomed to the APA style of citation and now I am required to follow Turabian's styles of citations feels a little petrifying but also awakening to the reality of research. For this paper, I used UK conventions of grammar and mechanics which I am much used to though EUCLID recommends US English. "EUCLID also recommends using American English, but both versions are obviously accepted" (ibid.). I hope to learn and master US English as fast as I can which I should be able to use in the upcoming papers. Although I have previously taken short courses online, long-distance learning is a new concept to me, and one I have found EUCLID organized in delivering the best via their course management and learning management systems.

EUCLID stresses on proper citation, however, while going through the student's orientation guidelines, and the learning management system site, I observed that the recommended Write Source 2000 (was written as one word) and Turabian manual were not fully cited. I particularly found it difficult to find Write Source 2000 as there were many versions of the same, by different authors.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2020. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

EUCLID. 2019. *Student Orientation Guidelines*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Turabian, Kate L. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 8th ed: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. 8th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.